

PULL-OFF TEST AND SIMULATION OF DUCTILE ADHESIVE BONDED COMPOSITE T-JOINTS

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Abstract

A systematic research project with focus on the failure analysis of ductile adhesive bonded composite structures is introduced in this paper. For this purpose, pull-off tests of laminated composite T-joints have been carried out. The constitutive response of adhesive layer with different mode mix ratios was tested with DCB, ENF and MMB tests. The adhesive response was implemented into a cohesive zone model, in which the mode I/II damage responses were unassociated with each other. Successful prediction of the present MMB tests proved the accuracy of the obtained adhesive response. The adhesive constitutive law has finally been used for the simulation of pull-off failure of T-joints. This paper reveals the effect of plastic yielding of the bondline on the overall structural response, which has successfully been captured by the experimentally determined constitutive law of the adhesive layer.

1 Introduction

During composite structure design and certification processes, the Building Block Approach (BBA) is usually applied [1]. It comprises analyses and associated tests at various levels of structural complexity, often beginning with small coupons and progressing through structural elements, sub-components, components, to finally the complete full-scale product. Tests at the lower levels of the pyramid are conducted to generate the material properties to feed appropriate analysis methods. By combining testing and analysis, theoretical predictions are validated by tests, test plans are guided by analysis, and the cost of the overall effort is reduced, while the degree of confidence and safety is increased [2]. The benefits from the interaction between experiments and analysis strongly rely on the predictive ability and accuracy of analytical methods. The T-joint (also named stringer stiffened

skin) is a typical connection in composite airframes and marine structures [3]. It transfers load between two orthogonally placed members meeting at a joint [4]. The aim of this paper is to present a new modeling method for analyzing adhesive bonded T-joints, and special attention was focused on the ductile adhesive response.

Modern toughened adhesives show significant plastic deformation before fracture, hence, the traditional analysis methods based on linear elastic fracture mechanics cannot work properly [5]. The cohesive zone model (CZM) has been increasingly used as it is able to predict both crack initiation and propagation, and can account for large fracture process zone. The constitutive law of the CZM is defined in terms of the traction stresses as a function of the separation and sliding between adjacent surfaces. There are mainly four factors that define a traction separation law: stiffness, strength, fracture energy and the shape of its enclosing curve [6]. Among these factors, the fracture energy is traditionally considered as most the critical parameter for obtaining a reliable prediction. Different shapes have been used for traction-separation laws, among which the bilinear law [7], trapezoidal law [8] and exponential law [9] are the most common ones. However, for ductile adhesives, the size of the failure process zone (FPZ) is comparable with the characteristic length of the considered structures, and the shape of the traction-separation laws may have significant influence on the simulation results [10]. A sophisticated model for the adhesive layer is thus necessary to correctly predict the failure behavior of ductile adhesive bonding.

In recent years, new methods based on the J-integral method have been employed to measure the constitutive law of adhesive layers [5, 11-14], and new cohesive laws may potentially be derived from

experimental results [15]. In this paper, ductile adhesive material was used for joining composite laminates into T-joints, and the T-joints were tested under pull-off loading. Comprehensive debonding tests of adhesive layers ranged from pure mode I to pure mode II were for the first time carried out in the author's group. The experimentally determined constitutive law for the adhesive layer was implemented into a cohesive zone model for simulating the pull-off failure of the T-joints.

Fig. 1. Test configuration of T-joints

Fig. 2. Mixed mode bending test, double cantilever beam and end notched flexure test

2. Experiments

2.1. Pull-off Test

The T-joints were manufactured by bonding three pieces of laminates together with adhesive. The adherend laminates were made by 8 layers of woven fabric of T300 carbon fibre. The epoxy resin was injected into the dry fibre architecture by the vacuum infusion method. The laminates were cured

at room temperature for 24 h and then post cured in the oven for 4 h at 80 °C. The adhesive was applied on solvent cleaned adherend surfaces, whereas glass beads were mixed into it to control its thickness of $280 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$. 3M 2216 epoxy adhesive was used for making both the T-joint specimen and debonding test specimen (introduced in the next section), which have been cured at 66°C for 2h.

The test fixture is shown in Fig.1, MMB tests were carried out with 6 different mode mix ratios. All tests are summarized in Table.1. The tests were carried out on a screw-driven static test machine; the strain rate was 2 mm/min.

2.2. Debonding Test of Adhesive Layer

The double cantilever beam (DCB) test [16], end notched flexure (ENF) test [8] and mixed mode bending (MMB) test [17] were employed in this work to get the local constitutive response of adhesive layer. The adherend laminates was made of T300/Epoxy, the production process introduced in Section 2.1 was also used here. The 13 μm - thick Kapton film was inserted between adherends to make the initial crack, which was smeared with mould release agent to prevent it from sticking with the adhesive. Glass beads of 1% weight fraction were used to obtain a constant adhesive thickness of $280 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$, which is the same as the adhesive layer thickness of the T-joints. The thickness of the adhesive layer is measured by optical microscopy after curing. DCB, ENF and six series of MMB tests were carried out, which are summarized in Table.1.

Table.1. Test configuration for DCB, ENF and MMB tests

ϕ	Number	$2L$ (mm)	a (mm)	c (mm)
0	4	-	40	-
0.26	4	150	52	150.6
0.33	5	150	52	110.0
0.44	4	150	52	83.0
0.59	4	150	52	63.6
0.74	4	150	52	49.5
0.86	4	150	52	41.2
1	4	130	40	-

The fracture energy can be calculated as follows [14, 18]:

$$J_I = \frac{12a^2}{E_f h^3 b^2} P_1^2 + P_1 (w'_1 - w'_2) \quad (1-a)$$

$$J_{II} = \frac{9a_0^2}{16E_f b^2 h^3} P_{II}^2 + \frac{3v}{8bh} P_{II} - \frac{9}{128kb^2 h^2} P_{II}^2 \quad (1-b)$$

where J_I is the mode I fracture energy of the DCB test or the mode I fracture energy components of the MMB test; J_{II} is the mode II fracture energy of the ENF test or the mode II fracture energy component of the MMB test. The MMB is considered here as a superposition of the DCB and the ENF test, and its mode I/II load components are calculated with [19]:

$$P_I = \frac{3c - L}{4L} P + \frac{3c_g - L}{4L} m \quad (2-a)$$

$$P_{II} = \frac{(c_g + L)m + (c + L)P}{L} \quad (2-b)$$

where P_I is the equivalent load for the DCB beam, P_{II} is the equivalent load for the ENF beam, m is the mass of the lever beam, c_g is the distance between the center of mass of the beam and the middle nose, and c is the distance between the loading point and the middle of the nose as shown in Fig.2. On the base of the J-integral theory, the local constitutive response of adhesive the layer can be obtained by:

$$\sigma(w) = \frac{dJ_I}{dw} \quad (3-a)$$

$$\tau_{xy}(v) = \frac{dJ_{II}}{dv} \quad (3-b)$$

Fig. 3. Displacement field at the initial crack tip

The deformation near the initial crack tip was recorded during the test with two cameras. The displacement field was then analysed with digital image correlation (DIC) methods. The shear and opening deformation of the adhesive layer are defined as the difference of the longitudinal and vertical displacements its two boundaries with regard to the actual orientation of the adhesive layer, which is calculated as follows [11]:

$$v = (U_{up} - U_{down}) \cos \lambda - (V_{up} - V_{down}) \sin \lambda + t \sin \lambda \quad (4-a)$$

$$w = (\cos \lambda - 1)t - (U_{down} - U_{up}) \sin \lambda - (V_{down} - V_{up}) \cos \lambda \quad (4-b)$$

where t is the thickness of adhesive layer. The rigid body rotation λ of the adhesive layer needs to be considered when calculating the deformation at the initial crack tip:

$$\lambda = \frac{w'_1 + w'_2}{2} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 4. Finite element model for (a) T-joint and (b) MMB test

3 Numerical Simulation

3.1 T-joint model

A finite element model for the adhesive bonded T-joint was built (Fig. 3) according to the test configuration. The laminates were modeled with continuous shell elements, and cohesive elements were inserted per every two layers to simulate the

delamination failure. The adhesive layer was modeled as a combination of an elastic substrate with finite thickness (0.28 mm) and a thin layer of cohesive elements. The triangular areas of the T-joints were filled with adhesive; their damage response is unknown, as the failure process and the corresponding damage evolution law of the adhesive layer is thickness dependent [20, 21]. However, plastic yielding and subsequent cracking occurred only in the thin strip near the interface (see Fig.10), so it is assumed that the damage evolution was the same as the adhesive layer.

The experimentally obtained adhesive properties were implemented into the FEM for predicting the debonding process. The delamination cracks within the composite adherends were simulated by the traditional bilinear cohesive law [22]. A quadratic nominal stress criterion is used to determine the initiation of damage:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma^0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau^0}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (6)$$

where σ^0 and τ^0 are the tensile and shear strength respectively. An energy based criterion is introduced to estimate the complete failure of cohesive elements:

$$\frac{G_I}{G_I^C} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{II}^C} = 1 \quad (7)$$

where G_I^C and G_{II}^C are the mode I/II critical strain energy release rates of the composite laminate; these are determined by test. All the cohesive parameters are depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Bilinear cohesive law for delamination simulation

Fig. 6 Fracture energy for different mode mix ratios

Fig. 7. Failure mechanisms of adhesive layer

3.2 MMB test model

The MMB test was simulated here to validate the experimentally obtained adhesive constitutive law. As shown in Fig. 4, The loading block and lever beam were assumed to be rigid bodies while the adherend laminates were modeled with continuum shell elements. The debonding process was simulated with cohesive elements, and the obtained constitutive law was employed.

4. Results and discussions

4.1 mixed mode constitutive law of adhesive layer

The mixed mode fracture energy and mode I/II components were presented in Fig. 6 as a function of true mode mix ratio: $\phi = J_{II}/J_M$. The J_I parameter lies in the range of 1-2 N/mm, it slightly increases with ϕ until $\phi = 0.59$, and then it starts decreasing. The J_{II} parameter shows a much stronger dependence on ϕ than J_I , and it increases monotonously with ϕ in a quadratic manner. The mixed mode fracture energy J_M increases from 2

Fig. 8. Mixed mode constitutive law of the adhesive layer

N/mm to 8 N/mm as ϕ increases from 0.26 to 0.86. The MMB test method presented here, combined with DCB and ENF tests, supplies a complete envelop of fracture energy ranging from pure tension to pure shear.

The fracture morphology of the adhesive material under tension/shear combined load was investigated with SEM. As shown in Fig. 7, several micro cracks were formed in front of the macro crack tip. Cavitation was found in the material far away from the micro crack boundary, indicating widely distributed plastic deformation over the adhesive thickness.

The mode I/II constitutive law can be evaluated by differentiating the fracture energy w.r.t. to the deformation at the initial crack tip. The polynomial fit of mode I/II and mixed mode traction-separation curves are plotted in Fig. 8. Slight dependence of the mode I response on the mode mix ratio can be observed, while the mode II traction stress increases significantly as the adhesive undergoes more shear deformation. The critical displacement for the complete failure of the adhesive layer was around 0.2-0.6 mm, which increased with the mode mix ratio. A new cohesive zone model was then developed on the base of the constitutive law, which allowed different damage evolutions of mode I/II responses.

Fig. 9. Load-displacement curves of MMB tests and simulation

4.2. MMB simulation

The MMB tests with different mode mix ratio were simulated here. The predicted load-

displacement curves were compared with experimental results, Fig. 9. The FEM results gained good correlation with tests in terms of both the stiffness and the critical failure load. The MMB beam stiffness degraded gradually before the load started to decrease because of the nonlinear response of the adhesive layer. The tension and shear displacements at the initial crack tip were found to increase non-proportionally, as the deformation was initially shear dominated, and the tension displacements became dominant after plastic yielding. This phenomenon is attributed to the difference between mode I and mode II damage evolution process. As shown in Fig. 10, the experimentally measured adhesive constitutive law and its FEM application reproduced the deformation path reasonably well. Hence, the local constitutive laws obtained from DCB, ENF and MMB tests are reliable; these were used for the analysis of the T-joint described in the next section.

Fig. 10. Tension-shear deformation path at initial crack tip

4.3 Failure of T-joints

The failure process of two T-joints is presented in Fig. 11 where the horizontal tensile strain of test-*a* was calculated with DIC. Due to the discontinuity of that displacement, the peak values of the tension strain were not accurate after crack initiation. However, the distribution of the tension strain was able to capture the deformation history and make it easy to show the location of cracks. The concentrated tension strain in the adhesive layer was recorded. This large deformation caused plastic yielding of the adhesive layer, as a strain whitening

zone was observed in test-*b* that indicates significant plastic deformation. With increasing load, a crack emerged in terms of delamination in test-*a*, which may be caused by the high bending moment at the corner. Tensile stress was found to be responsible for the delamination failure here [23]. The visible crack, initiated within the adhesive layer for test-*b*, propagated near the interface between the adhesive layer and the laminates. By increasing load, adhesive failure and multiple delamination cracks can be found in all tests.

Fig. 11. Two different failure modes of T-joints: (a) initiated with delamination; (b) initiated with debonding

The failure process predicted with FEM is shown in Fig. 12. The FPZ of the adhesive layer in FEM corresponds well to the plastic deformation and voids formation process in test. Delamination emerged earlier than debonding failure in FEM,

which was followed by adhesive failure and multiple delamination cracks. Hence, two distinctive failure modes were observed in the pull-off test of the adhesive bonded T-joints: debonding and delamination; both were predicted by FEM reasonably well.

Fig. 12. Failure process of T-joints predicted with FEM

Each failure progress in Fig. 11 is captured in the load-displacement curves in Fig. 13. The plastic yielding and debonding of the adhesive layer resulted in noticeable decrease of the T-joint stiffness. The sharp drops in the load-displacement curve were caused by delamination failure of the

composite laminates. The nonlinearity of the FEM results can also be observed, which was attributed to the failure process zone within the adhesive layer as shown in Fig. 12. The sharp drop of loading capacity was caused by delamination behavior. The FEM overestimated the maximum load as compared to the experiments (to some extent), this may be caused by defects on the T-joint specimen such as voids and resin rich areas (see Fig. 11). However, the FEM has shown its ability to predict the nonlinear response of T-joints caused by the failure process within the adhesive layer, and the FEM did agree with tests reasonably well.

Fig.13 load-displacement curves of T-joints

5. Conclusions

For the out-of-plane loading case of bonded composite T-joints, significant plastic deformation was observed in the adhesive layer, which has a noticeable effect on the overall failure behavior of bonded T-joints. The experimentally determined response of the adhesive layer was used for the numerical simulation of the pull-off tests. The good agreement between the simulation and the experiments demonstrates the applicability of the present numerical model. The numerical model may potentially be used for the analysis of other adhesive bonded structures as well

References

1. *Composite Materials Handbook*, D.o. Defence, Editor 2002. p. 586.
2. Feraboli, P., et al., *Predictive modeling of an energy-absorbing sandwich structural concept using the building block approach*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2010. **41**(6): p. 774-786.

3. Koh, T.M., S. Feih, and A.P. Mouritz, *Experimental determination of the structural properties and strengthening mechanisms of z-pinned composite T-joints*. Composite Structures, 2011. **93**(9): p. 2222-2230.
4. Cui, H. and Y.L. Li, *Failure of Composite T-Joints in Bending with Through-the-Thickness Reinforcement: Stitching Vs Z-Pinning*. Key Engineering Materials, 2012. **525-526**: p. 233-236.
5. Zhu, Y., K.M. Liechti, and K. Ravi-Chandar, *Direct extraction of rate-dependent traction–separation laws for polyurea/steel interfaces*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2009. **46**(1): p. 31-51.
6. Alfano, G., *On the influence of the shape of the interface law on the application of cohesive-zone models*. Composites Science and Technology, 2006. **66**(6): p. 723-730.
7. Jung Lee, M., et al., *Determination of cohesive parameters for a mixed-mode cohesive zone model*. International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives, 2010. **30**(5): p. 322-328.
8. de Moura, M.F.S.F., R.D.S.G. Campilho, and J.P.M. Gonçalves, *Pure mode II fracture characterization of composite bonded joints*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2009. **46**(6): p. 1589-1595.
9. van den Bosch, M.J., P.J.G. Schreurs, and M.G.D. Geers, *An improved description of the exponential Xu and Needleman cohesive zone law for mixed-mode decohesion*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2006. **73**(9): p. 1220-1234.
10. Sills, R.B. and M.D. Thouless, *The effect of cohesive-law parameters on mixed-mode fracture*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2012.
11. Högberg, J.L., B.F. Sørensen, and U. Stigh, *Constitutive behaviour of mixed mode loaded adhesive layer*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2007. **44**(25-26): p. 8335-8354.
12. Ji, G., Z. Ouyang, and G. Li, *Effects of bondline thickness on Mode-II interfacial laws of bonded laminated composite plate*. International Journal of Fracture, 2010. **168**(2): p. 197-207.
13. Ji, G., et al., *Effects of adhesive thickness on global and local Mode-I interfacial fracture of bonded joints*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2010. **47**(18-19): p. 2445-2458.
14. Leffler, K., K.S. Alfredsson, and U. Stigh, *Shear behaviour of adhesive layers*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2007. **44**(2): p. 530-545.
15. Högberg, J.L., *Mixed mode cohesive law*. International Journal of Fracture, 2006. **141**(3-4): p. 549-559.
16. Biel, A. and U. Stigh, *Effects of constitutive parameters on the accuracy of measured fracture energy using the DCB-specimen*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2008. **75**(10): p. 2968-2983.
17. Reeder, J.R. and J.R. Crews, *The mixed mode bending method for delamination testing* AIAA Journal, 1990. **28**(7): p. 7.
18. Cui, H., *Measurement of Mode II constitutive law for ductive adhesive*, 2013: Submitted to EFM.
19. Cui, H., S. Koussios, and Y. Li, *Constitutive Law of Adhesive Layer Measured with Mixed Mode Bending Test*, 2013.
20. Azari, S., M. Papini, and J.K. Spelt, *Effect of adhesive thickness on fatigue and fracture of toughened epoxy joints – Part II: Analysis and finite element modeling*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2011. **78**(1): p. 138-152.
21. Azari, S., M. Papini, and J.K. Spelt, *Effect of adhesive thickness on fatigue and fracture of toughened epoxy joints – Part I: Experiments*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2011. **78**(1): p. 153-162.
22. Turon, A., et al., *An engineering solution for mesh size effects in the simulation of delamination using cohesive zone models*. Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 2007. **74**(10): p. 1665-1682.
23. IJperlaan, R.M., *Test methods in support of the resin system choice for the production of the Donkervoort V-Card chassis*. MSc report. Department of Structural Integrity and Composites, Delft University of Technology, Delft, 2013.